

Material Permittivity and Conductivity Estimation From 2 to 260 GHz and Extension of the ITU-R P.2040 Model at Frequency Above 100 GHz

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Abstract—This paper analyzes the frequency-dependent electromagnetic characteristics of usual building materials such as mortar, glass or wood. Reflection and transmission losses are measured from 2 to 260 GHz and the related permittivity and conductivity are estimated. Results are compared with the ITU-R 2040-0 model that is mainly defined for frequency below 100 GHz. As suggested by the ITU model, the permittivity does not depend on the frequency and the conductivity increases with the frequency. However, reflection and transmission losses for frequency above 100 GHz may be strongly impacted by the material inhomogeneity or surface roughness that generates a frequency small-scale fading not predicted by the ITU model.

Index Terms—permittivity, conductivity, reflection loss, transmission loss, sub-THz, 6G

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical models such as ray tracing or ray launching models use a geographical database to compute all possible paths (direct, reflected, diffracted, diffused paths) between two or more points such as transmitter, receiver, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, relay, etc. These models are consequently frequently used for the performance evaluation of wireless radio interfaces [1][2]. The path amplitude is given by physical laws according to the interaction type between the electromagnetic (EM) wave and the environment. For instance, the direct path amplitude is given by the free space path loss equation, the diffracted path amplitude is given either by the knife-edge diffraction theory or by the Geometrical Theory of Diffraction / Uniform Theory of Diffraction, the reflected or transmitted path amplitude is given by the Fresnel equations. Compared to other physical phenomena losses, reflection and transmission losses depend on two material properties, the permittivity and conductivity, that may be frequency dependent. Hence, a physical model shall include a material table indicating the material permittivity and conductivity and, if necessary, how these parameters change with frequency. Many simulations refer to the International Telecommunication Union Radio-communication (ITU-R) P.2040-0 model [3] that is mainly valid up to 100 GHz. The ITU model may be not valid for 6G simulations where sub-THz frequencies up to 300 GHz are considered [4][5]. The goal of this paper is to discuss the ITU model validity for frequencies above 100 GHz. The analysis is based on contiguous material reflection and transmission loss measurements from 2 to 260 GHz.

This work extends previous work from the same authors presented in [6][7] by including new materials, estimating the permittivity/conductivity and pushing the upper frequency limit up to 260 GHz. More details regarding the theoretical model, the data processing, the measurement results and a literature review on material characteristics can be found in [8]

II. THEORETICAL MODEL AND ITU MODEL

In usual human environments, EM waves travel from a transmitter to a receiver located in the air and interact with building materials that may be considered as homogeneous isotropic low-loss dielectrics. Building materials are usually represented by a smooth-surface slab with thickness d as indicated in Fig. 1. The slab may be a glass window, concrete wall, plasterboard partition wall, etc.

Fig. 1. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ definition at normal incidence.

Fig. 1 illustrates the different paths created by the interaction between the EM wave and the slab. As the wave reaches the first material interface, a part of the wave is reflected, and the rest is transmitted through the material. The transmitted part from the first material interface penetrates through the material, and it is attenuated due to the penetration loss. Arriving to the second interface, a part of the wave will be transmitted, and the rest will be reflected. Likewise, multiple reflections are created inside the slab. In the following, for the sake of simplicity, only transmitted paths 1 and 2 (named 1T and 2T) and reflected paths 1 and 2 (named 1R and 2R) will be considered, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Let's define μ_0 and ϵ_0 the vacuum permeability and permittivity respectively, and ϵ_r and σ the slab relative

permittivity and conductivity, respectively. We denote $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ the frequency-dependent reflection and transmission transfer functions (TF) of the material slab whereas r and t are the reflection and transmission TF at the air-dielectric interface. p is the penetration TF inside the material. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ are analytically defined according to (1). r , t , ϵ_r and σ are potentially frequency-dependent, but for clarity reasons, it does not appear in the equations.

$$H_r^{Mod}(f) = r - \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p^2 r \quad H_t^{Mod}(f) = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p - \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p^3 r^2 \quad (1)$$

The ITU recommendation P.2040-3 [3] proposes a constant permittivity value regardless the frequency and expresses the frequency-dependent conductivity σ as $\sigma = a f^b$. ϵ_r , a and b are given for some materials such as plasterboard or glass. $H_r^{ITU}(f)$ and $H_t^{ITU}(f)$ are $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ applying the ITU model. $H_r^{ITU}(f)$ and $H_t^{ITU}(f)$ are illustrated in Fig. 2 for the glass ($d=8$ mm, $\epsilon_r=6.25$, $\sigma=0.0043f^{1.19}$) and the plasterboard ($d=13$ mm, $\epsilon_r=1.99$, $\sigma=0.0116f^{0.708}$). Fig. 2 illustrates the permittivity and conductivity impact on the reflection and transmission TF. We also observe the small-scale effects created by the interferences between the multipath created inside the slab. Due to the penetration loss increase with the frequency, small-scale effects tend to become less relevant at high frequencies.

Fig. 2. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ power profiles

As a first approach, the discussion about the ITU model validity above 100 GHz may be divided in two sub-discussions. The first sub-discussion is about the validity of the ITU theoretical framework. For instance, does the permittivity remain constant and the conductivity model by $a f^b$? Are the conductivity and permittivity still relevant parameters to compute reflection and transmission losses? The second sub-discussion is about the numerical values of ϵ_r , a and b . Shall they be updated to process correctly reflection and transmission losses? An ITU-like model was defined to help the analysis related to the first sub-discussion. This model is called ITUF and keeps the same theoretical approach of the ITU model but parameters ϵ_r , a and b are fitted on measurement presented in this paper. We define $H_r^{ITUF}(f)$ and $H_t^{ITUF}(f)$ the transfer functions $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ applying the ITUF model. In the following sections, the data analysis and model comparison will be mainly based on power profiles. A pp prefix added to a complex vector indicates the vector power profile. For instance,

$pp_H_r^{Mod}(f)$ is the power profile of $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and is equal to $10 \text{Log}_{10}(|H_r^{Mod}(f)|^2)$.

III. MEASUREMENT SETUP AND DATA PROCESSING

The measurement equipment is based on a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) and frequency extenders that can measure S parameters from 2 to 260 GHz. The measurement is divided into contiguous sub-bands defined by the frequency limits of the VNA, extenders, or antennas (2-30 GHz, 30-50 GHz, 50-75 GHz, 75-110 GHz, 110-170 GHz, 170-260 GHz). Antennas are dual-ridge Ultra-Wideband antennas for frequencies below 50 GHz and standard horn pyramidal antennas for frequencies above 50 GHz. Fig. 3 illustrates the mechanical part that allows a free space measurement for both transmission and reflection. The material under test (MUT) was placed at normal incidence between the two antennas in the material holder middle. Fig. 3 gives some slab examples.

Common building materials were measured. They are grouped in category depending on the material construction properties or the material function:

- Glass: mineral glass, plexiglass
- Plasterboard: BA13 and BA18
- Wood and its derivatives: plywood, Medium Density Fiberboard (MDF), melamine-faced chipboard.
- Concrete-like materials: mortar, cellular concrete
- Flooring tiles: vinyl, ceramic, carpet
- Thermal insulation materials: polystyrene, glass wool ceiling tile

Fig. 3. Measurement setup

For each frequency sub-band, the MUT measurement is preceded by two reference measurements, one in free space, the other with a metallic plate inserted into the MUT holder. We note $S_{11}^{FS}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{FS}(f)$ the S parameters measured by the VNA in free space and $S_{11}^{Met}(f)$ the S_{11} parameter measured with the metallic plate. When reference measurements are completed, slabs are put in the MUT holder and material measurements are proceeded. The measurement is performed at 3 points separated by 10 cm as illustrated by Fig. 3. The raw material measurements are denoted by $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{Meas}(f)$ for reflection and transmission measurements, respectively. We denote by $H_r^{Mut}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mut}(f)$ the intrinsic MUT reflection and transmission TF. They are computed according to (2)

$$H_r^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{11}^{Meas}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]}{TG[S_{11}^{Met}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]} \quad H_t^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{21}^{Meas}(f)]}{TG[S_{21}^{FS}(f)]} \quad (2)$$

TG[.] is the time gating operator. It is a temporal filter applied on the iFFT of S parameters that rejects all undesirable components that are not a physical interaction between the EM wave and the MUT. Fig. 4 illustrates the time gating effect for $H_r^{MUT}(f)$ processing. Environment reflections and the antenna back response residual part after subtraction are rejected from $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$. We define $h_r^{Mut}(t)$ and $h_i^{Mut}(t)$ the inverse Fourier Transform of $H_r^{Mut}(f)$ and $H_i^{Mut}(f)$.

Fig. 4. Time Gating effect on $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$

IV. PERMITTIVITY AND CONDUCTIVITY ESTIMATION

As the measurement presented in this work are complex measurement over very large bandwidths, it is possible to resolve in the time domain the multipath described in the theoretical part. For instance, Fig. 5 shows $pp_h_r^{Mut}(t)$ for the plexiglass at different frequency ranges. Path 1R and 2R can be clearly identified. Consequently, we apply separate estimation methods for the permittivity and conductivity. First, the permittivity is estimated by two different methods based either on the delay of transmitted paths or on the amplitude of reflected paths. We will only consider path 1R amplitude and path 1T delay as illustrated in Fig. 6 because second order paths are often below the noise level at the highest frequencies.

Fig. 5. $pp_h_r^{Mut}(t)$ for plexiglass

The initial measurement subbands were slightly rearranged to define nine new subbands of about 30 GHz bandwidth (2-30 GHz, 30-50 GHz, 50-75 GHz, 75-110 GHz, 110-140 GHz, 140-170 GHz, 170-200 GHz, 200-230 GHz, 230-260 GHz). An analyzed bandwidth of roughly 30 GHz is a good trade-off to

keep a good resolution for the path detection, to consider a constant value for the permittivity and to assess the large-scale permittivity frequency dependency.

Fig. 6. Permittivity estimation

Method 1 is based on the delay. Let's define t_{P1T} the delay of path 1T, c the wave celerity in vacuum, v the wave celerity in material. ϵ_r is calculated as expressed in (3)

$$v = \frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}} = \frac{d}{t_{P1T} + d/c} \Rightarrow \epsilon_r = \left(\frac{t_{1T} * c}{d} + 1 \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Method 2 is based on the amplitude. Let's define h_r^{IR} the amplitude of path 1R. ϵ_r can be calculated as in (4).

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_r} - 1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r} + 1} \Rightarrow \epsilon_r = \left(\frac{r + 1}{r - 1} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 7. Estimation comparison

Fig. 7 shows the permittivities estimated for the plexiglass, mortar and chipboard. The permittivity estimation is sometimes unreliable for rough surface materials or inhomogeneous materials or multi-layer materials because $h_r^{Mut}(t)$ or $h_i^{Mut}(t)$ are not enough resolved to detect without any ambiguity path 1R or path 1T. For instance, as illustrated in Fig. 8, the mortar permittivity was not estimated by method 1 above 140 GHz. Permittivities estimated by method 1 and method 2 are similar for most of the materials but diverge for some materials when the frequency increase. We can observe in Fig. 7 that the

permittivity estimated by method 2 for the mortar decreases with frequency whereas the permittivity estimated by method 1 remains constant. It can be explained by the scattering due to the mortar rough surface that increases the loss of the specular reflection [9][10]. We can also observe that the chipboard permittivity estimated by method 2 strongly increases with frequency, whereas the permittivity estimated by method 1 remains constant. It is certainly due to the thin melamine layer at the chipboard surface, but the fine physical explanation is still under investigation. It will be presented in a future scientific paper.

Fig. 8. $pp_{H_i^{Mut}}(t)$ for mortar

Permittivity values estimated by method 1 are more representative of the material electrical properties and less dependent of the material surface state. Consequently, they are more relevant to assess the permittivity frequency dependency. They are reported in Fig. 9 for various materials. It confirms that the permittivity is independent of the frequency even at frequency above 100 GHz. The final permittivity value reported in Table 1 is averaged over the different frequency bands and both estimation methods when permittivity values are available or meaningful.

Fig. 9. Material permittivity

The conductivity estimation was not performed by detecting path 1T amplitude for each frequency subband as the conductivity decreases with frequency and as the transmission losses are highly impacted by the material inhomogeneity.

Consequently, a simple and robust approach is to estimate parameters a and b by an iterative approach in order to minimize the error between $pp_{H_i^{Mut}}(f)$ and $pp_{H_i^{ITUF}}(f)$. The conductivity is estimated assuming the constant permittivity as indicated hereabove. Fig. 10 illustrates the conductivity frequency dependency by plotting the attenuation rate α equal to $\frac{\sigma}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r}}$.

Fig. 10. Material attenuation rate

V. COMPARISON BETWEEN MEASUREMENTS AND ITUF MODEL

Fig. 11 shows $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ or $pp_{H_i^{Mut}}(f)$ for three typical materials: plexiglass, mortar with moderate surface roughness, and melamine faced chipboard. The experimental results are compared with the ITUF model and when possible, with the ITU model.

For clarity reasons, the ITU model is computed by considering only path 1T in transmission and path 1R in reflexion. $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ or $pp_{H_i^{Mut}}(f)$ for the plexiglass are very well fitted by the ITUF model, even at frequencies above 100 GHz. No difference is observed between the three measurement points. We found similar results for the mineral glass, and we can conclude that the ITUF model can be used without any restriction when the material is homogeneous with a flat surface. For all other materials, the ITUF model remains valid up to a frequency that depends on the material structure. Regarding reflection losses, the mortar with moderate roughness is a good example to illustrate the scattering impact on the ITUF performance. We clearly observe in Fig. 11 that the regular periodic small-scale fading disappears at 60 GHz and is replaced by an irregular fading with no correlation between the three points. This effect is due to the scattering on the surface. The fading is no more due to the complex recombination between path 1R and path 2R but is due to the complex recombination of scattered components. The scattering increases the reflection loss average value and makes the ITUF model inaccurate or not valid as the difference model/measurement may be higher than 10 dB. We also observed for some materials such as the MDF, glasswool or chipboard that $pp_{H_r^{Mut}}(f)$ increases with frequency as illustrated by the laminated chipboard example in Fig. 11. The

$pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ increase compared to $pp_{H_r}^{ITUF}(f)$ is generally limited to a few dB.

The analysis of transmission results leads to similar conclusions. The frequency-dependent conductivity can be well modeled by the ITUF model “on average”. The absolute difference between $pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_{H_r}^{ITUF}(f)$ is generally about a few dB for frequencies less than 60 GHz but may exceed 10 dB for frequencies above 100 GHz. For instance, the ITUF model agrees with mortar or chipboard results up to 60

GHz, but some variations appear above 60 GHz and the three measurement point results are uncorrelated. Fig. 8 shows $pp_{h_i}^{Mut}(t)$ for the mortar at different sub-bands. Path 1T is highly attenuated, and some delayed components appear at frequencies above 100 GHz. It suggests that the volume diffuse scattered component inside the material due to the material inhomogeneity becomes preponderant compared to the specular transmission.

Fig. 11. $pp_{H_r}^{Mut}(f)$ or $pp_{H_i}^{Mut}(f)$ compared with ITU and ITUF models. Plexiglass (a1,b1), Mortar (a2,b2), Melamine chipboard (a3,b3)

TABLE I. ESTIMATED AND ITU PERMITTIVITY AND CONDUCTIVITY.

Category	Material	Relative permittivity ϵ_r		Conductivity σ (S/m)			
		ITUF model	ITU model	ITUF model		ITU model	
				a	b	a	b
Glass	Mineral glass	6.2	6.27	0.005	1.2	0.0043	1.1925
	Plexiglass	2.65		0.0001	1.5		
Plasterboard	BA13	2.5	2.94	0.0004	1.35	0.0116	0.7076
	BA18	2.9		0.0004	1.4		
Wood and derivatives	MDF	2.4		0.006	1.0		
	Plywood	2	1.99	0.007	1.0	0.0047	1.0718
	Chipboard	2.4	2.58	0.007	1.1	0.0217	0.78
Concrete-like materials	Aerated concrete	1.9		0.002	1.3		
	Mortar 1	4.6	5.31	0.002	1.5	0.0326	0.8095
	Mortar 2	6.4		0.004	1.4		
Flooring	Vinyl tile	3.8		0.0002	1.6		
	Ceramic tile	5.9		0.005	1.2		
Insulation plates	Polystyrene	1.05		0.000008	1.1		
	Glass wool tile 1	1.2	1.5	0.0002	1.35	0.0005	1.1634
	Glass wool tile 2	1.2	1.5	0.002	1.2		

VI. ITU MODEL VALIDATION UP 300 GHz

The estimated permittivity and conductivity are reported in table 1 and compared with the ITU model values when available. There is a good agreement between the permittivity experimental values and those provided by ITU. Consequently, we could extend the permittivity ITU model for frequency up to 300 GHz. But many building materials are composite or multi-layered materials. When the wavelength decreases, these materials cannot still be considered as homogeneous with flat surface, and the reflection loss may be incorrectly modeled by the permittivity-dependent Fresnel equations. Applying scattering models [9][10] or a multi-layered model [3] is one option but this option is complex to implement in ray tracing, increases the processing time and makes more complicated the digital map description. Above 100 GHz, a simple model evolution could be the definition of correction factors to take into account the reflection loss decrease or increase compared to the model. This approach would require multipoint measurements to investigate statistically the reflection loss of covered materials (melamine, wallpaper, painting, varnish, etc) or rough surface materials.

Estimated parameters a and b agree with those given by the ITU for the glass and plywood but are sometimes very different. For instance, we never found b values less than 1. It implies that the ITU model underestimates the penetration loss at high frequencies for materials having a b value less than 1. Fig. 11 illustrates the model error for the chipboard and mortar. The recommendation is to consider the dielectric parameters fitted by our measurement at least for the mortar and chipboard. Regarding the transmission loss variation around the model due to the inhomogeneity at high frequencies, the ITU model could be improved by adding to $H_t^{\text{ITU}}(f)$ a statistical variable but as indicated here above for the reflection loss, this approach requires new measurements.

VII. CONCLUSION

The analysis shows that the ITU model needs to be improved for frequencies above 100 GHz by considering the material surface state or the volume inhomogeneity for the reflection and transmission coefficient processing. But as a first step, the ITU model could be used as it is in many simulations related to 6G sub-THz scenarios. Reflection loss errors due to rough surfaces may be not a concern in office environment, shopping mall, airport, etc as most of the material are quite smooth. Transmission loss errors due to the material inhomogeneity may be not a concern as they concern high transmission losses at high frequencies. Simulating a transmission error of 20 dB instead of 30 dB may not significantly impact system simulation if we consider that a transmission loss higher than 20 dB corresponds to a blockage. Future work will be focused on the impact of the material surface state on the reflection coefficient as proposed in section VI.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partly funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe/JU SNS project Hexa-X-II (Grant Agreement no. 101095759). The authors would like to thank all people and especially Eric Seguenot from the CREMANT laboratory (joint laboratory between Orange Labs and Univ. Côte d'Azur) for their help and support during the measurement campaigns.

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